

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers,

welcome to the eight issue of volume three. I want to thank all authors for their contributions and the editorial board for their review effort. I hope you will enjoy the papers.

This issue contains 8 articles: U. M. Borghoff, R. Pareschi: Information Technology for Knowledge Management; W. Prinz, A. Syri: Two Complementary Tools for the Cooperation in a Ministerial Environment; C. Simone, M. Divitin: Ariadne: Supporting Coordination through a Flexible Use of the Knowledge on Work Processes; S. Buckingham Shum: Negotiating the Construction and Reconstruction of Organisational Memories; O. Kühn, A. Abecker: Corporate Memories for Knowledge Management in Industrial Practice: Prospects and Challenges; D. Rösner, B. Grote, K. Hartmann, B. Höfling: From Natural Language Documents to Sharable Product Knowledge: A Knowledge Engineering Approach; H. Sorensen, A. O'Riordan, C. O'Riordan: Profiling with the INFormer Text Filtering Agent; G. Amati, D. D'Aloisi, V. Giannini, F. Ubaldini: A Framework for Filtering News and Managing Distributed Data

Yours sincerely,

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Graz / Austria, August 28, 1997.
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